

Original Research

Application of Hyperspectral Imaging with Deep Learning to Identify Varieties of Rice Seed and Leaf

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Abstract

A Seed adulteration is a noteworthy issue that is causing concern for both planters and consumers and potentially leading to substantial losses. Consequently, the accurate identification of seed variety is crucial. This study investigated the application of hyperspectral imaging (HSI) integrated with deep learning (DL) algorithms for the identification of rice seed and leaf varieties. Hyperspectral data were collected and preprocessed from six distinct rice varieties (7,586 rice seeds and 2,160 rice leaves) using a near-infrared hyperspectral camera with 943.08–1657.47 nm spectral range. The data were corrected using white and dark reference images to reduce noise and lighting variations. Spectral information was extracted, preprocessed, and analyzed, and in each sample, a region of interest (ROI) was defined. We build various classification models (LR, RF, SVC, LSTM & CNN) to assess the classification task. Owing to its' automatically extracting features, the CNN model was able to outperform the others, achieving test accuracy of 86.03% and 91.89% for seeds and leaves, respectively. SVC also performed quite well, especially for seeds (88.4% accuracy), while conventional ML models like LR and RF showed comparatively lesser accuracy, which points out their limitations in dealing with complex non-linear relationships, as is the case with hyperspectral data. These results first demonstrated the substantial promise that combining hyperspectral imaging (HSI) and deep learning (DL) holds for fast, non-invasive, precise variety recognition of rice. It can have major implications in seed quality evaluation, breeding programs, and precision agriculture where this method would permit good screening right from the seeds and leaves for preferred characteristics to increase yields.

Keywords: Hyperspectral Imaging (HSI); Deep Learning; Rice Seed Classification; Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN); Seed Quality Assessment; Plants Identification.

Introduction

Rice is the staple food of a large part of the world's population, having great diversity in its varieties, which are adapted to different environments, nutritional values, and flavors [1,2]. In the crop year 2024/2025, global rice consumption and production were projected to be 530.23 million and 532.66 million metric tons, all due to a fixable notion illustrated in Fig. 1, with much growth over ten years, which is about 12%. Rice seeds are harvested as food for consumers and as seeds for the following sowing season. Owing to the vast planting areas across villages, towns, countries, and continents, different varieties of rice seeds have been developed to adapt to changes in growth environments and improve nutrition and flavors [3]. For breeders, farmers, and consumers, as well as other stakeholders, this diversity in varieties must be carefully identified and classified [4]. For the breeders it is important to correctly identify varieties for the preservation

of genetic purity of their breeding lines and for the selection of desirable traits [5,6]. Farmers require this information to make informed decisions about which varieties to plant based on local conditions and market demands [4]. On the other hand, consumers benefit from accurate labeling and traceability to ensure that the specific type of rice they want is what they are getting. The conventional rice variety identification techniques, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) and Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometer (GC-MS), will mostly depend on visual inspection, which is subjective and a very long process [7,8]; it has been applied generally only on a few samples [9,10]. Other options include laboratory-based methods like DNA fingerprinting [11], which though correct, are costly and demand extensive expertise and equipment [12]. Thus, given the challenges faced with conventional techniques of rice variety identification, there is a pressing need for innovative and cost-effective alternatives that can provide rapid and accurate results.

Hyperspectral imaging is an emerging technology that has found diverse applications in agriculture, including crop management, yield prediction, disease detection, and monitoring of land usage, water resources, and soil conditions [13]. Hyperspectral imaging captures both spatial and spectral information from the sample, which might give a non-destructive and potentially more efficient alternative for the identification of rice variety [14,15]. Current studies often concentrate on specific spectral ranges, potentially overlooking valuable information present in other regions of the electromagnetic spectrum [16]. Exploring a broader spectral range could reveal unique spectral signatures that differentiate rice varieties more effectively [17]. Hyperspectral imaging is highly innovative tech that captures hundreds of narrow, contiguous light bands reflected or given off by a sample [18]. This results in a hyperspectral cube rich in data with spectral signatures that serve as fingerprints that correspond to the biochemical composition and physical structure of the sample [19].

An influential branch of artificial intelligence called deep learning has shown a state-of-the-art performance when it comes to analyzing large, complex datasets such as hyperspectral images [20,21]. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) are one of the widely used models, have the ability to automatically and transparently learn hierarchical features in images [22,23]. Deep learning makes it possible to detect and learn complex patterns inherent in data without prior manual feature extraction, much like the working of the human brain [24-26]. In hyperspectral image analysis, CNNs have been applied to classify 2D and 3D hyperspectral remote sensing data. As CNNs are typically used for the classification of 2D and 3D data, attempts at using CNNs for 1D spectral data pose a challenge. Subsequently, researchers made attempts to build CNNs for spectral data analysis. Acquarelli et al. (2017) suggested a CNN framework for vibrational spectroscopic data analysis [27]. Liu et al. (2017) suggested a CNN framework for Raman spectra recognition [28]. Regarding input data, the performance and accuracy of deep learning models vary based on the specific data utilized, making it essential to examine the types of input data researchers have used [29].

Hyperspectral imaging in tandem with deep learning has the potential to transform the identification of rice varieties by providing an avenue for the high-throughput systems capable of accurately categorizing rice seeds and leaves based on their spectral signatures. The rationale behind this is that, instead of relying on domain knowledge to perform traditional feature extraction steps [30]. Running on this deep learning algorithm, the subtle spectral features differences in rice variety types that can not be recognized by naked-eye observation or which are not easily detected using traditional systematic and analytical methods, may be able to be discovered [20, 31]. Utilizing these technologies in conjunction with one another will enable a more reliable and efficient means of variety identification that would greatly benefit rice breeding programs, agricultural practices, and food quality control [32]. Some conventional feature-engineered methods have been proved by previous studies to enhance accuracy in computer vision applications through CNNs as a general extractor [33]. For instance, Zhou et al. (2017) used an 8-layer CNN to optimize the VGG-Net model structure to extract characteristics from images of the key tomato sections, including fruit, blossom, leaf, and stem [34]. A novel technique for classifying plant diseases was introduced by Khan et al. (2018) using a four-step algorithm [35]. The initial step involved the use of a correlation coefficient approach for the segmentation of the illness regions. Thereafter, the extraction of deep features is then done using two pre-trained models VGG-16 and Caffe AlexNet. In this scenario, GA was employed to select the most distinguishing features. Ultimately, multi-class SVM was used to classify the chosen features which achieved 98.6% accuracy. Quan et al. (2019) used A Faster R-CNN model in a different work to automatically extract picture attributes and identify maize seedlings at various growth stages [36]. To identify 40 distinct varieties of wheat grain, a CNN architecture VGG-16 was engaged in research by Ozkan et al. (2019) to extract features [37]. The extracted features were then used for an SVM classifier, whereas they asserted that the model was 100% accurate. Ozkan et al. (2021) using VGG16 with SVM achieved 99% accuracy in classifying 50 hyperspectral wheat samples [38]. One study applied hyperspectral data with migration learning to classification of ten soybean varieties using six models: AlexNet, ResNet18, Xception, InceptionV3, NASNetLarge and DenseNet201 achieving over 90% accuracy [39]. The feasibility of haploid corn seed classification was evidenced with hyperspectral images by Liao et al. (2019). The image attributes were extracted using a VGG-19 network. They obtained a 96.32% correct classification rate [40]. For trait extraction of seven cotton seed types, Susu et al. (2019) built models utilizing CNN and ResNet [41]. They used SVM

models, logistic regression (LR), and partial least squares discriminant analysis (PLS-DA) to classify cotton seeds. The model accuracy was reported as 80%. In Khan et al. (2020a), a new approach was shown which used multi-SVM to identify fruit diseases achieving an accuracy above 97% and they adapted VGG-s and AlexNet for pulling out deep traits [42]. An automated way of classifying cucumber leaf diseases was presented by Khan et al. (2020b) [43]. A top classification exactness of 98.08% was reached by the writers using two pre-trained models such as VGG-19 and VGG-M for feature extraction plus multi-class SVM for classification. Kong et al. (2013) used hyperspectral imaging to classify 4 varieties of rice seeds, and most of the discriminant models using full spectra and selected optimal wavelengths obtained good classification results (over 80%) [44]. Classifying eight varieties of wheat resulted in over 90% accuracy in hyperspectral imaging, as per the study conducted by Mahesh et al. (2008) [45]. Yang et al. (2016) used hyperspectral imaging to classify 14 maize varieties [46]. Spectral information was taken from each individual seed, and discriminant models were built using both full spectra and optimal wavelengths. The classification accuracy of most maize varieties was over 90%. Liu et al. (2016) classified soybeans, maize, and rice with hyperspectral imaging. Optimal wavelengths were then determined from extracted spectral data [47]. Discriminant models using full spectra and optimal wavelengths all obtained good performances.

Plant species and cultivar identification have been the hyperspectral imaging application domain under the purview of plant science. Hyperspectral imaging can identify plant species or varieties within a species non-destructively, drawing on the spectral signatures unique to different plants [48]. Various studies on rice cultivar identification associated with this approach have been made, such as research by Arias et al. (2021) [49]. Liú et al. (2013) used hyperspectral imaging to distinguish six indica rice cultivars combined with chemometrics [50]. Itakura et al (2020) utilized both leaf and tree trunk images which significantly improved the tree species classification accuracy, making it handy for ecological, monitoring, conservation, tourism [51]. Wu & Zhang (2019) effectively identifies tree species in complex forest types in southern China combined airborne hyperspectral data and LiDAR data with 94.68% classification accuracy using SVM classifier [52]. HSI along with machine learning algorithms was used by Mahmoodi-Eshkaftaki et al. (2025), to classify plants having therapeutic properties into categories- medicinal, edible, and ornamental based on their organs' spectral reflectance achieving more than 95% accuracy [53]. Utilizing hyperspectral imaging, Yang & Kan (2022) successfully identified eight tree species at the leaf level [54]. Saranya et al. (2024) have shown great classification precision using hyperspectral imaging via a ResNet-MHSA-CNN strategy that not only fetches high-resolution features but also secures long-range dependencies, achieving 99.74% accuracy on the Indian Pines dataset [55]. Hyperspectral imaging combined with support vector machine effectively discriminate nitrogen fertilizer levels in tree plants, improving plantation management. They classified three different nitrogen treatments 100% accurately using fused hyperspectral data (Wang et al. 2018) [56]. Carvalho et al. (2013) collected hyperspectral reflectance data from leaves and flowers of *J. vulgaris* to evaluate their relevance to predict the plant fitness [57]. Spectra were acquired with leaves and flowers attached to the plant between 350 and 2500 nm and analyzed by QDA. Significant differences were found between spectra of leaves and flowers as well as during the season. The results of the cross-validation lead to a percentage of correct assignments according to the succession stage (old, medium, and young) of 92.3% for leaves and 94.4% for flowers being the corresponding values of the prediction set 56.1% and 65.0%. Kelman et al. (2013) investigated the adaptation of approaches to hyperspectral imaging for the pixel-level classification of five kinds of Chinese tea, using visible light hyperspectral spectroscopy [58]. Gongalla et al. (2024) proposed deep learning, merging the random forest RF model with O-ConvNet-RF plus hyperspectral imaging for classifying tea leaves as green, yellow, and black [59]. Spectral signature of HSI was applied to classify green teas [60] and wuyuan green tea stalks separation from tea [61]. Along with machine learning, HSI enables the scalable monitoring of plant health and attributes in complex ecosystems. For instance, a study has demonstrated the effectiveness of hyperspectral imaging for plant classification through an efficient segmentation workflow using sparse mixed-scale convolution neural networks, authorizing high accuracy with minimal labeled data; thus, enabling monitoring of plant health in fabricated ecosystems [62]. Thus, this setup would transform rice breeding phenotyping, letting breeders screen and pick traits wanted in a sharper, smarter way. In addition, the potential use of hyperspectral imaging and deep learning can be used to implement quality control in the rice industry to ensure that consumers receive the correct rice type with the craved characteristics. Hyperspectral imaging has altered how farmers farm, helping them learn when to make an early smart choice about the crop [32].

In this study, as a feature extractor from hyperspectral imaging, deep learning was employed to classify six different types of rice seeds and six different types of rice leaves, irrespective of how they were oriented on the conveyor. The major idea here is checking if hyperspectral imaging along with deep learning can be used for spotting different kinds of rice seeds and young plants. This study encompasses the development of an appropriate classification model structure and the visualization of classification results obtained by the optimal model and explores the capability of hyperspectral imaging to distinguish rice seed varieties, which is crucial for quality control and precision agriculture. The efficiency of different machine learning classifiers, such as an LSTM, SVC, and CNN for rice seed and leaf classification has been evaluated.

Fig. 1- Global rice production & consumption statistics a) consumption b) production

Materials and Methods

Sample Preparation

A total of 7586 rice seeds and 2160 rice leaves were selected for this experiment Fig. 2(c). The rice seeds and leaves included six different varieties: Jiahua1 (hereinafter referred to as Jh1), Nanjing46 (hereinafter referred to as Nj46), Xiushui121 (hereinafter referred to as Xs121), Xiushui134 (hereinafter referred to as Xs134), Zhehujing26 (hereinafter referred to as Zhj26), and Zhejing100 (hereinafter referred to as Zj100) appearance Fig. 2(a,b). All the rice seeds were collected and sealed in a plastic bag and were naturally air-dried to be considered as experimental samples. These varieties had great differences in growth environment, growth time, disease resistance, insect resistance, taste, and so on. Different types of seeds were neatly placed on the sample table with a spacing of approximately 5nm to ensure that all the seeds had the same collection environment. Hyperspectral image data of all the seeds were collected six times owing to the large number of seeds.

After the rice seed hyperspectral image acquisition, the seeds were sown on the experimental fields in Institute of Crop Science, Huzhou Academy of Agricultural Sciences. The growth of the rice plants were regularly managed. During the seedling stage, the rice leaves of the six varieties were cut and placed in plastic bags and stored in the box with ice. The leaves were then taken to the laboratory for hyperspectral image acquisition. Before hyperspectral image acquisition, the leaves were wiped by dry and clean papers to make the leaves dry and clean. Therefore, for each of the six rice leaves, HSI data were collected as well.

Fig. 2- a) Rice seeds appearance; b) rice leaves appearance c) number of rice seed and leaf samples used

Near-infrared Hyperspectral Image Acquisition and Correction

Near-infrared hyperspectral images (NIR-HIS) were extracted from six distinct varieties of rice seeds and six different types of rice leaves for this investigation. Images were captured using the HSI acquisition platform, the Lab Scanner (Specim, Spectral Imaging Ltd., Oulu, Finland) and the FX17 HSI camera of the same company from Oulu, Finland Fig. 3. The spectral range covered by these devices is 943.080–1657.47 nm. The lab scanner is powered by two arrays of 35W halogen lights each. One row of data is acquired in terms of both spatial and spectral information by the sample stage, which is a high-gloss black surface with a white calibration whiteboard. The sample stage on the stepper motor control lab scanner pushes forward for imaging at a speed of 25.30 mm/s. Lumo Scanner 2020 (Specim, Spectral Imaging Ltd., Oulu, Finland) software controls the FX17 camera and lab scanner. Hyperspectral images of 224 spectral channels were obtained per scan. In order to reduce the effect of dark current and standardize the light intensity, the initial hyperspectral image needs to be corrected using both a white reference image and a dark reference image [63,64]. Reflectance hyperspectral images should then be available following correction.

$$R = \frac{I - D}{W - D} \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

where R stands for the corrected image, I for the original image, W for the white reference image, and D for the dark reference image. The white reference image is obtained by shooting a white calibration whiteboard, while the dark reference image is taken after the lens is fully covered with a lens cap. The head and tail bands are removed, and the wavelength range from 943.08 nm to 1657.47 nm is retained to prevent system instability and the influence of noise in the spectral data in this study [65]. Each seed in the hyperspectral image was considered a region of interest (ROI) for this study, and the average spectrum of each cell within the ROI was calculated to create a spectral vector that represented the seed sample. This was done within the experimental accuracy range.

Fig. 3- Hyperspectral imaging system

Spectra Extraction and Preprocessing

To increase the precision and rigor of the experimental data collection in this study, an algorithm that can automatically extract the spectrum of rice samples in batches was created.

A hyperspectral image of one hundred rice seeds was collected at a time as an example of an acquisition experiment. Each seed's location was ascertained and divided using the linked components after the RGB image had been binarized

to eliminate the background. Then, using the x-axis coordinates at the center point position of the connected components, each ten seeds was sorted from right to left. Each seed produced a specific spectrum, resulting in a total of 7586 spectra of rice seeds. All real spectra would be used to enhance the data. The flowchart is shown in Fig. 4. The obtained spectral information required preprocessing due to severe noise in the front-end and back-end bands [31, 66,67], so the wavelength range of 943.08 to 1657.47 nm was preserved. Lastly, the pixel value and the number of pixels in each connected component were counted, the total pixel value and the number of pixels were divided, and the required average spectral information was obtained.

For experimentation, nine leaves hyperspectral images were collected at a time and then, to focus on the relevant regions of the rice leaves, both the hyperspectral and RGB images were cropped to remove unwanted areas, ensuring that only the regions of interest were processed. Therefore, a single band from the hyperspectral data employed for masking, in which rice leaves display strong contrast against the background, was utilized along with a threshold applied to that band to create binary masks isolating regions containing rice leaves from the background. Following this process, connected component analysis was used in identifying individual samples of rice leaves within these masks; areas corresponding to potential noise were filtered out based on small size. Therefore, 2160 spectra of rice leaves were stored. To obtain the 1D spectral data, the average reflectance values across all spectral bands were calculated for each rice leaf sample.

Fig. 4- Spectral extraction workflow of rice

Classification Model Development

Random Forest (RF)

This is a machine-agency implementation of Random Forests, a technique in machine learning that can be used for both classification and regression tasks. Due to its versatility and effectiveness, Random Forests are one of the most widely used algorithms for classification problems. Generally, it is based on the idea of combining predictions based on several decision trees, which increases the stability and accuracy of the model compared to one model. Random forests stand out for their ability to work with large data sets with many features and can provide characteristics important to the model, thus allowing for the identification of leading variables determining predictions. In this study, we used a grid search that was performed to select optimal parameters in C: $[10^{-4} - 10^4]$, penalty: L2.

Logistical Regression (LR)

A classic machine learning algorithm, logistic regression has the advantage of avoiding erroneous hypothetical distributions. In this study, we used the grid search hyperparameter tuning technique to find the optimal set of hyperparameters, L2 regularization, and C was chosen for 0.0001 to 10000 to evaluate the classification model. The LR model's random_state and max_iter were set to 1110 and 1500, respectively.

Support Vector Classification (SVC)

Support vector machine (SVM): a classification algorithm that works wonderfully for the classification task and also for regression, commonly used in academic research [68,69]. Support vector classification (SVC) is based on statistical learning theory and is suitable for linear tasks [70]. The basic concept for SVC is to find a hyperplane that separates two classes with the maximum margin possible. SVC is popular because of its strength in handling high-dimensionality data as well as its efficiency in linear and non-linear classification issues. Another great factor adding to the agility of SVC is the method of the "kernel trick" which allows data to be shifted into higher-dimensional vector spaces where linear separation can happen, not bearing the cost of computational effort for mapping data into these spaces. It uses a kernel

function such as linear kernel, polynomial kernel, or radial basis function (RBF) kernel. However, there are issues to take into account with the use of SVC, like its computational complexity, sensitivity to noise, and trouble in understanding decision boundaries when dimensions are high. This research used the polynomial kernel and a grid search was performed to select optimal parameters in C: $[10^{-3} - 10^2]$ and gamma: $[10^{-3} - 10^2]$.

Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)

Long Short-Term Memory networks belong to that variety of artificial neural networks which can learn from time series data, depending on long-range short dependencies typical of that data. The peculiar gating mechanisms employed by Long Short-Term Memory networks (namely, forget gate, input gate, and output gate) allow these systems to explicitly choose what information to remember or to forget and overcome some limitations standard recurrent neural networks are subject to namely the vanishing gradient problem. In the case of LSTMs, the sequence length and batch size of the input data need to be taken into account. In general, longer sequences can better record temporal dependencies but also make computations more expensive. The optimal hyperparameters for an LSTM model to classify different seed varieties involve a combination of tuning strategies and specific parameter choices. Researches prove that model performance greatly depends on hyperparameters such as optimizer, activation function, batch size as well as the number of LSTM layers. For this study Fig. 5, we used epoch: 500, batch size: 96, and the learning rate was set to lr:0.0001

Fig. 5- LSTM model architecture structure

Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)

A convolutional neural network is a unique feedforward neural network that is integrated into convolution operations [71]. In addition to having a large number of neurons, convolution operations work with activation functions and normalization techniques, which results in excellent feature extraction and mapping capabilities [65, 72]. The algorithms of CNNs utilize feature extraction and dimensionality reduction to achieve input-to-output mapping [73]. A CNN architecture is constituted by various combinations of convolutional layers, activation layers, pooling layers, flattening layers, and FC layers [74]. The feature graph serves as the convolution layer's unit, and each unit is connected to the block of the preceding feature graph by the filter group [75]. The down-sampling method by the convolutional layer helps capture the main spectral information [76]. The pooling layer provides dimensionality reduction. The ReLU activation function can lessen the impact of gradient vanishing in the gradient-based optimization method, which has the benefit of avoiding overfitting. Batch normalization can improve training efficacy for the model [76]. Consequently, the ReLU activation function and BN are employed in the self-constructed CNN of this study.

In this study, the hyperparameters of the network were selected after the experimentation of many results obtained by varying the number of convolutional and FC layers, the size and number of the convolutional filters, the learning rate, and the batch size. The architecture of the CNN built in this study had two convolutional layers, a flatten layer, two FC layers, and one output layer (or softmax layer) corresponding to the 6 output classes Fig. 6. A kernel size of 4 and a stride size of 1 with zero padding were used in the first two convolutional layers whose filters were set to 8 and 16, respectively. Batch normalization (BN) was used after both the convolutional layers. The feature maps extracted from the second convolution block were flattened into a one-dimensional vector and the results were subsequently fed into the first FC layer. The number of neurons in the two FC layers was successively decreased from 752 to 6. A rectified linear unit (ReLU) nonlinearity was applied in each convolutional layer and 1st FC layer. The ReLU activation function performs a threshold operation as follows:

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} \alpha x, & x < 0 \\ x, & x \geq 0 \end{cases} \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Where x and f(x) are the input and output of the activation function, respectively. The negative slope coefficient α was set to its default value of 0.3. The adam optimizer with the default parameters $\beta_1, \beta_2 = (0.9, 0.999)$, $\text{weight_decay}=1e-5$, and categorical cross-entropy loss function was utilized to train the model. The weights of all layers were initialized randomly; the learning rate and batch size were set to 0.005 and 2400, respectively. The network was trained for 1000 epochs in the considered experiment.

Fig. 6- Architecture structure of CNN classification model

Model Evaluation and Software Tools

The article's experimental flowchart is shown in Fig. 7. Using 1D spectrum as input with 200 features following noise reduction. Classification accuracy, precision, and recall(sensitivity) along with the F1-score were used in this study to evaluate the performance of the model which is evaluated based on the following formula:

$$\text{Accuracy (\%)} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + FP + FN + TN} \times 100\% \text{-----(3)}$$

$$\text{Precision (\%)} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \times 100\% \text{-----(4)}$$

$$\text{Recall (\%)} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \times 100\% \text{-----(5)}$$

Where TP is true positive, TN is true negative, FP is false positive, and FN is false negative. A larger value for each metric indicates improved performance of the respective model. Python version 3.8 and scikit-learn version 1.0.2 were used to develop the models in SVC, LR, and LSTM for processing HSI data and building classification models in this work; PyTorch 1.10.2 was taken as the base framework for the deep learning model. Training of the deep model was accelerated by the NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3060 laptop GPU. Data analyses were performed using computers with Intel (R) Core (TM) i7-11800H (2.3GHz) and 16G RAM.

Fig. 7- Experimental workflow

Results and Discussions

Reflectance Spectra Analysis

Spectral information is the most important characteristic of HSIs and plays a vital role in the classification tasks [77]. The mean reflectance spectra extracted from both rice seed and leaf varieties in the spectral range of 943.08–1657.47 nm (total of 200 spectral wavelengths) and the standard deviation of six types of rice seeds and leaves are shown in Fig. 8. In general, all the absorbance spectrum curves of different varieties have similar trends and the location of the peak of the six types of rice seeds was very similar indicating that there may be more common characteristics between the six types of rice seeds and leaves; however, there exists some difference in the reflectance intensity. Therefore, it is difficult to discriminate the variety based on raw diffuse reflectance spectra. It is necessary to build some models for identifying the rice varieties.

The spectra at around 950-1300nm, the reflectance remains relatively stable with some deviation. On the contrary, there is a notable dip between 1300-1450nm. The reflectance stabilizes again with light variation after 1450nm. The spectral difference of rice seeds and the wavelength differences were most obvious at 1400nm Fig. 8(a).

Therefore, for the majority of the spectrum of rice leaves, the reflectance remains between 0.3 and 0.5, suggesting that vegetation typically responds in the NIR range. The reflectance is relatively stable at around 950-1300nm and has a sharp

dip near 1400nm. The reflectance increases again and stabilizes after 1450nm wavelengths Fig. 8 (b).

Fig. 8- Average spectra after pre-processed spectrum a) rice seeds b) rice leaves

Classification Result Analysis

To obtain better classification results, the 7586 real seeds spectral data and 2160 leaves spectral data from six rice varieties were divided in the laboratory into training, validation, and test sets according to the ratio of 8:1:1. In this study, three machine learning methods- random forest(RF), support vector classification (SVC), and logistic regression (LR) and two deep learning models LSTM and CNN were used to establish a spectral classification model to identify rice varieties. The parameters for LR, RF, SVC, and LSTM were described in previous sections. The number of CNN training epochs=260 and the learning rate=0.001 for evaluating rice seed data; epochs=1000 and the learning rate=0.005 were set to evaluate rice leaf data. We selected the best round of results as a showcase.

Rice Seed

The classification results on the rice seeds dataset are presented in Table 1. The five different machine learning models' performance was demonstrated, evaluating through training, validation, and test accuracies. The Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) outperforms other classification algorithms and gained a training accuracy of 94.79% with a drop to 88.01% and 86.03% in validation accuracy and test accuracy respectively indicating overfitting. This means that CNN is good at learning patterns of the training data, but still its' generalization ability could be further enhanced. The Support Vector Classifier (SVC) exhibited remarkable stability across all datasets. It achieved 92.78%, 88.14%, and 88.40% accuracies with training, validation, and testing, respectively. Such high performance shows that SVC generalizes well to the unseen data, indicating that SVC was also a robust choice to perform classification in this case. On the other hand, the Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) model presents stable performance operating on training, validation, and test sets with an accuracy of 87.43%, 86.43%, and 83.14%, respectively. Its performance is decent but slightly worse than CNN and SVC. The Random Forest Classifier (RFC) has reached a training accuracy of 100% but severe overfitting has been observed in validation accuracy |61.62%| and test accuracy |59.42%| as reflected in RFC. Such a dramatic decrease in performance demonstrates support vector clustering generalizability over RFC to be non-existent due to its complexity. The Logistic Regression (LR) model can be observed to show the lowest performance out of all models with accuracies below 80% across all datasets. This highlights that the Logistic Regression (LR) being linear also suffers from an inability to reflect the complexity of the dataset and therefore fails to exploit inherent non-linear relationships in the data.

In conclusion, the experimental results show that CNN and SVC are the best models for rice seed classification, and the SVC classifier has greater generalization ability than CNN. The overfitting of RFC and poor performance of LR models show that these models are not adequate models for this task. Future work may take into consideration techniques that can reduce overfitting behavior exhibited by CNN; for instance, applying dropout layers or regularization and may also explore hybrid techniques merging attributes of both CNN and SVC. Such an analysis can help select which model may work better for crop variety identification.

Table 1- Classification results of different models on the rice seeds dataset

Material	Model	Accuracy		
		Training	Validation	Test
Seeds	CNN	0.9479	0.8801	0.8603
	LSTM	0.8743	0.8643	0.8314
	SVC	0.9278	0.8814	0.8840
	RFC	1	0.5942	0.5704

	LR	0.7714	0.7826	0.7706
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Rice Leaf

Table 2 presented the classification results of different machine learning models on the rice leaf dataset. It is evident that the Convolutional Neural Network model has impeccable training accuracy achieving an exquisite outcome of 100% and maintaining high validation and test accuracies of 91.67% and 91.89% in that order. This shows that CNN can learn complex features of the data, but possible overfitting is indicated by a small decrease in validation and test accuracies. The Random Forest Classifier also works well with a perfect training accuracy and a robust 89.18%, making it the second-best performing model. However, similar to CNN, there are signs of RFC being overfit, which may be improved with regularization or pruning. The LSTM model experienced a considerable drop in accuracy from the training to validation and test sets; it generalized poorly and overfitted. We have the Support Vector Classifier (SVC), which had moderate training and validation accuracies but fails to perform on the test set, indicating this algorithm will not be a good choice for this dataset. LR is the weakest model, which has low accuracies for all criteria, indicating that LR is unable to learn the data well, as it is not effective for more complex relationships.

In conclusion, CNN is the most effective model that can be achieved with this dataset; however, ways should be introduced to mitigate overfitting. Future research may investigate ensemble techniques integrating CNN and RFC. Additionally, it may focus on increasing generalization for LSTM and SVC via hyperparameter optimization and supplementary data. Logistic Regression should be eschewed for this task due to its suboptimal performance.

Table 2- Classification results of different models' on rice leaf dataset

Material	Model	Accuracy		
		Training	Validation	Test
Leaf	CNN	1	0.9167	0.9189
	LSTM	0.9053	0.7685	0.7252
	SVC	0.8815	0.8611	0.7567
	RFC	1	0.8703	0.8918
	LR	0.6265	0.6759	0.563

Classification Report of CNN Model

From the previous section, it is evident that CNN was the best model for rice variety identification. In this section, the classification report of the CNN model for each variety is presented. Fig. 9 depicts the confusion matrix, precision, recall, and F1-score of all 6 varieties where class 0 represents Jh1, class 1 represents Nj46, class 2 represents Xs121, class 3 represents Xs134, class 4 represents Zhj26, and class 5 represents Zj100.

In the confusion matrix diagonal elements are correct predictions where the actual class matches the predicted class and off-diagonal elements are misclassifications where the actual class doesn't match the predicted class. Every row in the confusion matrix represents a variety that belongs to an actual class, and every column represents a variety that belongs to a predicted class. Most of the anticipated and real spectra match, according to the confusion matrix's sparsity. The model achieved the best performance on the rice leaf. The model has performed outstandingly on class 3 Xs134 leaves (f1-score= 94.87%); out of 37 Xs134 leaves on the training set almost 100% and class 1 Nj46 seed (f1-score=95.40%), out of 120 Nj46 seeds on the training set 95% were correctly classified. On the contrary, the bottom value of the F1-score was 87.32% for the rice leaf Jh1 variety and 81.51% for the Xs121 rice seed variety. For this Jh1 leaf variety, out of 37, 83.78% of the spectra were correctly classified and for the Xs121 seed variety, out of 120, 90% of the spectra were correctly classified. Out of 2160 rice leaf spectra, 91.98% were correctly classified and out of 7586 rice seed spectra, 86.03% were correctly classified.

Fig. 9- Confusion matrix of CNN model classification report for a) leaf training set b) leaf validation set c) leaf test set d) seed training set e) seed validation set f) seed test set

Conclusion

The work highlighted its' promises much that hyperspectral imaging(HSI) coupled with deep learning(DL) would serve to identify rice seed and leaf varieties rapidly, non-destructively, and accurately. Employing high spectral resolution of hyperspectral imaging(HSI), along with strong pattern recognition abilities provided by means of deep learning(DL)-more specifically convolutional neural networks(CNNs)-this study classified six distinct rice types of seeds and foliage

with test accuracies of 86.03% and 91.89%, respectively. Results thus far have been preliminary but indicate that CNNs have advantages over traditional machine learning approaches such as logistic regression and random forest for the type of complex, high-dimensional data sets that are typical in hyperspectral imaging. This has great implications for seed quality assessment, breeding programs, and precision agriculture. A scalable and work-efficient option for screening seeds and leaves is the highlighted approach that could contribute to selecting desirable features and improving yield. Furthermore, the non-destructive nature of HSI ensures that seeds are preserved for future use. In future, research could optimize algorithms and extend the approach or improve model robustness further or to other crops and agricultural settings. Spectral signatures may vary with moisture, temperature, and growth stage. Future studies should incorporate these variables into the training data to improve model robustness. Controlled experiments under varying environmental conditions could help develop adaptive algorithms that compensate for such fluctuations. To increase the usability in resource-constrained settings (e.g., rural farms), future work should explore developing lightweight architecture of deep learning (e.g., MobileNet, EfficientNet) for edge devices in field applications.

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